

Characterisation of a cerebroside isolated from the leaves of *Datura metel*

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Datura metel, a plant well known for tropane alkaloids and withasteroids, yielded several sphingosine derivatives, one of which was characterised as (4*E*,8*Z*)-1-*O*-(β -D-glucopyranosyl)-*N*-(2'-hydroxyhexadecanoyl)-sphinga-4,8-dienine from comprehensive spectral analysis of its hexaacetate. This is the first report of the isolation of a cerebroside from *Datura* species.

Datura metel Linn. (Solanaceae) is well known for elaboration of tropane alkaloids¹ and withasteroids^{2,3} but the occurrence of sphingolipids from this source has not yet been reported. In quest of withasteroids, we made a thorough phytochemical investigation of different *Datura* species and isolated several sphingolipids in addition to withasteroids from *D. metel* and its relatives.

While most of these compounds were isolated only as complex mixtures, the one isolated from the polar fraction of the methanolic extract of the leaves of *D. metel* was fairly pure and this compound, provisionally designated as compound A, has been identified as a cerebroside (2) from comprehensive spectral analysis.

Results and Discussion

Compound A, C₄₀H₇₅NO₉ (MH⁺, *m/z* 714, m.p. 200–202°, [α]_D +7.7° (MeOH)), showed in its ir spectrum, bands for hydroxyl (3425 br cm⁻¹) and amide carbonyl (1637 cm⁻¹) functions. The polar nature of the compound indicated it to be a glycoside and this was verified by acid hydrolysis experiment which furnished glucose, a ninhydrin-positive compound (probably a primary amine) and a hexane-soluble substance which was considered to be a fatty acid from the observed soap-like properties of its alkaline solution. This observation suggested the compound to be a cerebroside and its mass spectrum in FAB mode lent support to this assumption. The spectrum showed besides the hydrogen adduct molecular ion (MH⁺) peak at *m/z* 714 (14%), other significant ion peaks at *m/z* 696 (MH⁺-H₂O, 23%), 534 (MH⁺-C₆H₁₂O₆, 32%), 460 (MH⁺-255 + H, 16%), presumably by loss of *N*-acyl group and a base peak at *m/z* 262 (ion *a*) for the protonated sphingosine-type base moiety⁴. Acetylation of the compound with Ac₂O-pyridine yielded a hexaacetate (2a) which showed in its ¹H nmr spectrum signals for six acetoxymethyl groups between δ 1.98 and 2.2 and a six proton triplet at δ 0.89 for terminal methyl groups of two alkyl chains. Its FABMS showed an intense peak at *m/z* 906 (MH⁺-AcOH, 95%), 618 (MH⁺-tetraacetylglucose,

12%), 558 (906-tetraacetylglucose, 15%), 331 (ion *b*, 98%) and 262 (ion *a*, 92%).

The 500 MHz ¹H nmr spectrum of the hexaacetate showed two one-proton doublets, one at δ 6.32 (*J* 7 Hz) and the other at δ 4.48 (*J* 7.5 Hz) which were assigned respectively to H-N of the base moiety and the anomeric hydrogen of the acylated glucose unit (Table 1). Recognition of these two hydrogen signals permitted identification of signals for H-2/C-2, H-1/C-1, H-3/C-3, H-4/C-4 and H-5/C-5 of the sphingosine-type base moiety and of all the hydrogens and carbons of the sugar unit by making use of homo- and heteronuclear 2D-nmr methods. A comparison of ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data (Table 1) of this hexaacetate with the acetyl derivative of *N*- α -hydroxyoctadecanoyl-1-*O*- β -glucopyranosylsphingosine, isolated from the rhizomes and roots of *Euryale ferox*⁵, suggested a gross similarity of their structures and on this basis the isolated cerebroside was assigned the gross structure 1, in which the composition of R and R₁ remained to be settled.

Table 1. Nmr spectral data for cerebroside hexaacetate (2a) in CDCl₃

Position	¹ H, δ (m*, J in Hz)	¹³ C (ppm)**
1	3.62 (dd, 11.3, 4.4) 3.93 (dd, 11.3, 4)	66.9
2	4.3 (m)	50.4
3	5.32 (t, 7.2)	72.9
4, 8, 9	5.39 (3H, m)	124.5, 129.0, 131.6
5	5.82 (dt, 16.3, 6.3)	136.6
6	2.1	32.4
18	0.89 (t, 7)	14.1
2'	5.15 (dd, 7.5, 5)	72.5
3'	1.8 (m)	32.0
1''	4.48 (d, 7.5)	100.3
2''	4.95 (dd, 9.4, 7.5)	71.0
3''	5.18 (t, 9.4)	73.8
4''	5.08 (dd, 8.8, 7.5)	68.0
5''	3.7 (m)	71.8
6''	4.16 (dd, 12.5, 3.8) 4.26 (dd, 12.5, 5)	61.6
NH	6.32 (d, 7)	

* Multiplicity of signals.

** Assignments made on the basis of 2D ¹H-¹H and 2D ¹H-¹³C COSY experiments.

The ¹³C nmr spectrum of the parent molecule in CD₃OD showed an amide carbonyl signal at δ 178.0 which was, however, not clearly discernible in the spectrum of the hexaacetate taken in CDCl₃. The hexaacetate showed in its ¹³C nmr spectrum signals for six acetylcarbonyl carbons between δ 169.0 and 172.0 and nine oxycarbon signals between δ 61.6 and 100.3; six for the sugar unit, one for the methylene bearing the sugar unit and the remaining two for two secondary alcoholic carbons. The composition of R in structure 1, was settled from mass spectral analysis of the methyl ester of the acid obtained by methanolysis of the cerebroside with 2 N methanolic HCl. The EI mass spectrum of this methyl ester showed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 286 (22%) and an intense peak at *m/z* 227 (57%), formed by loss of -CO₂Me group. The genesis of an intense peak by loss of an alkoxycarbonyl group is rather characteristic of esters of α-hydroxy acids and on this basis the acid participating in *N*-acyl function was proved to be α-hydroxypalmitic acid. The appearance of a carbonyl hydrogen signal at δ 5.15 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5, 5 Hz) in the spectrum of the hexaacetate also supports α-hydroxy structure of the acyl moiety. The composition of R was thus settled as CH₃-(CH₂)₁₂.

The molecular formula of the cerebroside demands four double bond equivalence of which three are discernible in the gross structure 1. Obviously, the fourth one must be present in R₁ unit. The presence of two disubstituted olefins, as revealed from ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra of the hexaacetate (δ 5.82, 1H, dt, *J* 16.3, 6.3 Hz; 5.39, 3H, complex m; δ 124.5, 129.0, 131.6, 136.6) also suggested the presence of an extra double bond in R₁. The position of this

extra double bond in sphingosine-type base moiety was settled to be between C-8 and C-9 from ¹H-¹H COSY experiment which revealed that H-5 resonating at δ 5.82 and one of the olefinic hydrogens of the complex 3H multiplet at δ 5.39 are separated by two vicinal allylic methylenes showing signals at δ 2.0 and 2.1. The base moiety was thus proved to be sphinga-4,8-dienine. While the coupling constant of H-5 indicates that the double bond between C-4 and C-5 of sphingadienine is *E*, that between C-8 and C-9 is considered to be *Z* because the appearance of three olefinic hydrogens (H-4, H-8 and H-9) as a complex multiplet at δ 5.39 is more consistent with 4*E*,8*Z*-base structure⁷ than with 4*E*,8*E*-sphingadienine⁴. In view of the *erythro*-configuration of naturally occurring sphingosine type bases, the compound was considered to have *erythro*-configuration which is also consistent with the resonance signal at δ 72.9 for C-3 and the coupling constant of H-3 (*J* 7.2 Hz)^{4-6,8}. The structure of the isolated cerebroside was thus advanced as 2, which is incidentally the same as that proposed for the antiulcerogenic cerebroside B_{1-b}, isolated from *Tetragonia tetragonoides*⁹ and synthesised by different groups of workers^{10,11}. While the m.p. and specific rotation of the natural product have not been reported, those of synthetic samples differ considerably. This is presumably due the difficulty in purification of this group of compounds. The m.p. of our compound is very close to that (194–196°) reported by Mori and Kinsho¹⁰ and the specific rotation value lies between the two reported values but differs significantly from that of its diastereoisomers¹¹. This is the first report of the isolation of a cerebroside from *Datura* species and we report for the first time the spectral data for the hexaacetate (2a).

While reports of isolation of sphingosine derivatives from marine organisms are quite common^{4,6,8} reports of isolation of phytosphingolipids are relatively rare.

Experimental

Plant material and extraction procedure were the same as that reported earlier¹². M.p. is uncorrected. ¹H nmr (500 MHz) and ¹³C nmr (125 MHz) spectra in CDCl₃ were recorded with reference to TMS. Silica gel (Qualigens, 60–120 mesh) and silica gel G (Qualigens) were used for cc and tlc respectively.

The CHCl₃-soluble fraction of the MeOH extract of the leaves of *D. metel* was chromatographed over silica gel and eluted initially with C₆H₆ and sequentially with C₆H₆-EtOAc mixtures, EtOAc and EtOAc-MeOH mixtures. Early fractions of EtOAc-MeOH (9 : 1) yielded sitosterol glucoside and later fractions furnished cerebroside (0.013%) m.p. 200–202°, [α]_D²⁰ +7.7° (*c* 0.58, MeOH).

Acetylation of 2 to 2a : A solution of 2 (40 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) and Ac₂O (3 ml) was left at room temperature overnight and then heated on a water-bath for

2 h. After usual work up, the acetylated product was extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract was dried and completely freed from solvent to give an amorphous white powder (Found : C, 64.18; H, 9.23; N, 1.12. $\text{C}_{52}\text{H}_{87}\text{NO}_{15}$ requires : C, 64.64; H, 9.07; N, 1.45%).

Methanolysis of cerebroside (2) : Cerebroside (2) was refluxed with 2 N methanolic HCl (3 ml) for 5 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with hexane (3×5 ml). The hexane layer was dried and evaporated to dryness to give methyl- α -hydroxypalmitate, m/z 286 (M^+), $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_3$.

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